

EFFECT OF AGEING ON THE VISCOSITY OF SOLS

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The effect of ageing on the sols of stannic hydroxide, ferric phosphate and vanadium pentoxide of different purities and dilutions, at variable shearing forces have been studied in this paper. The conclusions have been as follows:—(i) the viscosity of a concentrated sol increases on ageing and reaches a maximum value, which is followed by a decrease; (ii) the viscosity of a dilute sol decreases at first and then there is an increase followed by a decrease; (iii) the purer the sample, sooner the ageing takes place; (iv) the more dilute the sample, sooner the ageing takes place; (v) changes in the viscosity of a sol with ageing are more pronounced with concentrated sols than with dilute ones; (vi) higher the pressure, lower are the changes in viscosity of a sol with ageing.

The changes of viscosity on the ageing of sols have been investigated by number of workers. The results presented in this paper on the measurement of viscosities for the sols of stannic hydroxide, ferric phosphate and vanadium pentoxide obtained at their various stages of dialysis, and different dilutions, carried out at variable shearing forces, lead to the conclusion that the effect of ageing on the viscosity of the sols is intimately related with the purity and concentration of the sols. The concentrated sols, which are capable of developing the structural flow prominently, usually show an increase in the viscosity to a maximum with age.

In a number of communications Dhar and Chakravarty (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 42, 149; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 168, 209) have reported the influence of ageing on the viscosities of both organic and inorganic colloids and these authors have concluded that in general lyophilic colloids show an increase whilst the lyophobic ones are characterised by developing a decrease in their viscosities with time. This behaviour of the two types of colloids has been ascribed to the difference in the hydration of the colloids with age. Desai and co-workers (*Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1939, 2, ii) emphasize the considerable change in the physical properties of colloids on dialysis. It is also well known that the concentration of the sols remarkably affects their physical properties. In this paper we have therefore investigated the effect of age on viscosity of some sols of different purities and concentrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

The viscosity of the sols have been determined by an apparatus, similar to that of Farrow and Ostwald, and modified by Ayub and Ghosh (*Bull. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, 9, 149). The relative viscosity of the sols are given by

$$\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_w} = \frac{1/t_1 + 1/t_2}{1/t_1' + 1/t_2'}$$

where η_s is the viscosity of the sol at a definite temperature and pressure, and η_w is the viscosity of water under the same conditions, t_1 and t_2 represent the time of flow downwards and upwards the tube for water and t_1' and t_2' are the corresponding times for the sols. The accuracy of this apparatus has been described in a previous paper.

Stannic Hydroxide Sol

This sol was prepared by peptising a well washed stannic hydroxide precipitate by concentrated ammonia, which was removed to different amounts by dialysis carried out at different stages in cold. The various samples of sol at different stages of purities (A, A', A'', A''') were taken out and diluted to their one-third and one-ninth concentrations,

All these sols were stocked in glass-stoppered Jena bottles and their purities were determined from the ammonium radical present in the sols in the usual way. The results obtained for 23 c.c. of these sols mostly at a pressure of 30 cm. of water column, and temperature 30° are recorded below. In some cases the results of the measurement of viscosity at different shearing forces (care being taken to avoid turbulent flow) are also given.

TABLE I

Conc. of sol A = 45.16 g./l. of solid matter.
Conc. of NH_4^+ = 1.36 g./l.

Time.	Sol A.	Sol A/3.	Sol A/9.
0 days	1.1000	1.016	1.000
7	1.1207	1.013	1.000
20	1.1417	1.036	1.000
45	1.1478	1.041	1.023
61	1.1511	1.015	1.031
103	1.1650	1.000	1.000

TABLE II

Conc. of the sol A' = 42.40 g./l. of solid matter.
Conc. of NH_4^+ = 0.823 g./l.

Time.	Sol A'.	Sol A'/3.	Sol A'/9.
0 days	1.138	1.044	1.021
6	1.142	1.040	1.020
19	1.149	1.055	1.023
44	1.153	1.049	1.021
50	1.166	1.023	1.021
102	1.1540	1.019	1.011

TABLE III

Conc. of the sol A'' = 36.58 g./l. of solid matter.
Conc. of NH_4^+ = 0.501 g./l.

Time.	Sol A''.	Sol A''/3.	Sol A''/9.
0 days	1.189	1.057	1.023
14	1.199	1.024	1.015
21	1.214	1.055	1.027
43	1.205	1.058	1.030
57	1.205	1.049	1.011
99	1.192	1.029	1.005

TABLE IV

Conc. of Sol A''' = 39.92 g./l. of solid matter.
Conc. of NH_4^+ = 0.295 g./l.

Time.	Sol A'''.	Sol A'''/3.	Sol A'''/9.
0 days	1.206	1.068	1.033
10	1.230	1.064	1.030
21	1.243	1.058	1.040
42	1.246	1.067	1.053
45	1.204	1.052	1.041
90	1.191	1.038	1.014

TABLE V

η_{sp} of sol A at different pressures of water column in cm.

Time.	30 cm.	45 cm.
0 days	1.1000	1.088
7	1.1207	1.103
20	1.1417	1.114
45	1.1478	1.115
62	1.1511	1.122
104	1.1650	1.147

Ferric Phosphate Sol

The ferric phosphate sol was prepared by the interaction of ferric chloride and potassium dihydrogen phosphate. The sol thus obtained was dialysed to different extents, and the samples taken out at different stages of purity, which is estimated from the amounts of chloride radical per litre. Different samples were designated as B, B', B'', B'''. As before the volume of the sol taken was 23 c.c., pressure = 30 cm. of water and temperature = 30°.

TABLE VI

Conc. of the sol B = 51.52 g./l. of solid matter. Conc. of Cl^- ion = 0.236 g. ion/l.

Time.	Sol B.	Sol B/3.	Sol B/9.
0 days	1.120	1.029	1.011
12	1.120	1.023	1.009
33	1.148	1.019	1.000
50	1.153	1.014	1.000
65	1.163	1.009	1.000

TABLE VII

Conc. of the sol B' = 51.52 g./l. of solid matter. Conc. of Cl^- ion = 0.2360 g. ion/l.

Time.	Sol B'.	Sol B'/3.	Sol B'/9.
0 days	1.149	1.053	1.021
10	1.137	1.053	1.025
21	1.153	1.032	1.000
41	1.163	1.039	1.045
50	1.174	1.042	1.063

TABLE VIII

Conc. of the sol B'' = 34.67 g./l. of solid matter. Conc. of Cl^- ion = 0.0047 g. ion/l.

Time.	Sol B''.	Sol B''/3.	Sol B''/9.
0 days	1.271	1.076	1.029
7	1.285	1.053	1.013
28	1.313	1.052	1.000
45	1.406	1.068	1.000
61	1.575	1.028	1.000

TABLE IX

Conc. of the sol B^{II} = 31.63 g./l. of solid matter. Conc. of Cl^I = 0.0022 g. ion/l.

Time. o days	Sol B ^{II} .	Sol B ^{III} /3.	Sol B ^{II} /9.
5	1.428	1.108	1.041
26	1.547	1.096	1.007
49	1.561	1.101	1.073
58	1.563	1.101	1.039
	1.566	1.068	1.034

TABLE X

$\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_w}$ of sol B^{II} at different pressures of water column in cm.

Time. o days	30 cm.	45 cm.
7	1.271	1.245
28	1.285	1.276
45	1.313	1.306
61	1.406	1.343
	1.575	1.538

Vanadium Pentoxide Sol.

The sol was prepared by treating ammonium vanadate with concentrated HCl, in a pestle and mortar and mixed thoroughly till it became deep blood red. This precipitate of vanadium pentoxide was washed on a filter paper with distilled water, when the precipitate showed the tendency to peptisation. The whole precipitate was thoroughly shaken with an excess of water and the sol kept in a parchment paper for cold dialysis. Various samples were taken out at different stages of purity and designated as C, C', C'', C^{III}. As before the experiments were conducted with 23 c.c. of the sol at a pressure of 30 cm. of water and at 30°.

TABLE XI

Conc. of sol C = 12.012 g. of V₂O₅ per litre.

Time.	Sol C.	Sol C/3.	Sol C/9.
o days	1.123	1.032	1.016
12	1.142	1.050	1.019
26	1.150	1.051	1.019
52	1.204	1.050	1.019
70	1.239	1.043	1.000

TABLE XII

Conc. of sol C' = 11.466 g. of V₂O₅ per litre.

Time.	Sol C'.	Sol C'/3.	Sol'/9.
o days	1.136	1.047	1.021
10	1.152	1.030	1.015
24	1.163	1.036	1.030
50	1.171	1.043	1.032
68	1.215	1.040	1.030

TABLE XIII

Conc. of the sol C'' = 10.556 g. of V₂O₅ per litre.

Time.	Sol C''.	Sol C''/3.	Sol C''/9.
o days	1.139	1.054	1.012
8	1.145	1.042	1.008
22	1.153	1.046	1.038
47	1.157	1.048	1.040
65	1.192	1.045	1.000

TABLE XIV

Conc. of the sol C^{III} = 9.828 g. of V₂O₅ per litre.

Time.	Sol C ^{III} .	Sol C ^{III} /3.	Sol C ^{III} /9.
o days	1.147	1.049	1.020
5	1.155	1.036	1.007
22	1.163	1.047	1.020
47	1.170	1.048	1.020
65	1.127	1.041	1.013

TABLE XV

$\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_w}$ of sol C^{III} at different pressure of water column in cm.

Time.	20 cm.	30 cm.	95 cm.
o days	1.139	1.134	1.116
8	1.162	1.145	1.124
22	1.168	1.153	1.126
47	1.175	1.157	1.126
65	1.220	1.192	1.137

DISCUSSION

One of the properties of colloids affected by ageing of the sols is their viscosity. Our results have shown that in general the changes in the viscosities of these sols have been more prominent in the case of the concentrated sols than in the case of dilute ones. The viscosities of the pure concentrated sols of stannic hydroxide, ferric phosphate and the purest sample of vanadium pentoxide have a general tendency to increase with time. In some cases within a period of two to three months of observation, there is definite evidence of a tendency to decrease, for the viscosities of these sols, after they have attained the

maximum value. Similar changes in the viscosity of a sol of ceric hydroxide were recorded by Chakravarti, Ghosh and Dhar (*cf.* "Colloid Chemistry" by J. Alexander, Vol. II, p. 105). Davies, Oakes and Browne (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1526) also report that the viscosity of gelatine solution increases with time, and reaches a maximum in about twenty four hours, higher grades of gelatine may show greater increase in viscosity. In this connection it should be stated that this increase in viscosity to its maximum is more quickly attained for dilute and pure sols than for concentrated and impure sols. Thus in the case of the first three impure sols of vanadium pentoxide, the maximum increase in viscosity was not observed even in two and a half months of observation, and a decrease in the viscosity, from the maximum value for the concentrated sol was noted only with the purest sample of vanadium pentoxide.

In accordance with the views developed by Chakravarti and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) on the viscosity of sols, it may be suggested that with ageing the hydration of the colloid particles increases, reaches a maximum and then decreases owing to agglomeration of the particles, which results in a subsequent decrease in the viscosity. It will however be seen from Tables V, X and XV that the variations in the viscosity of these sols are more remarkable for measurements carried out at low pressures than at the higher ones. It may be therefore suggested that these variations of viscosities of the sols are intimately connected with the structure that is usually associated with the colloid particles of hydrated sols. It is possible that the increase in the viscosities of these sols on ageing in the earlier stages of the process is more due to this structure formation than due to the slight changes in the hydration of the colloid particles. Ghosh and co-workers (*Bull. Acad. Sci. U. P.* 1939) have emphasised the prominence of the structure flow for concentrated and pure sols, and hence this behaviour of the changes in viscosity on ageing is likely to be observed more with these sols than with dilute and impure ones.

It may be noted that for the dilute sols, though the variations in the viscosities with time are much less than for the concentrated ones, yet their behaviour is quite significant. For dilute sols, it has been generally found that there is first a decrease, and then an increase followed by a continuous fall in the viscosity with time. These results can be explained on the view already stated that in the case of the dilute sols, the structural flow being much less prominent, these sols first show the ordinary tendency to decrease in viscosity with age. When however these dilute sols have become considerably unstable on ageing (as will be shown in a subsequent paper) these sols may develop the structural flow and be similar in behaviour to the concentrated ones, showing an increase in viscosity followed by a decrease.

It may therefore be concluded that sols in general have a tendency to decrease in viscosity with age, either because of a lesser degree of hydration or due to Smoluchowski's electro-viscous effect due to the decrease in electric charge on colloidal particles with time. If however the sol is of a character that develops structural flow, as is usually true for highly viscous sols, it may show an increase in viscosity to a maximum and then a decrease with age. In the case of concentrated sols or such sols as contain some of the substances in true molecular species, developing the structural flow the time for observing the decrease in the viscosity of the sols may be long, as in the case with impure vanadium pentoxide sols.